

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF BLOOM'S TAXONOMY IN ANALYZING THE LIFE AND CREATION OF ISAJON SULTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11082582>

ABSTRACT: This article focuses on methods and methodical views aimed at increasing the level of analysis and study of Isajon Sultan's works. In this regard, Bloom's taxonomy has theoretical views on the recommendation to study Isajon Sultan's works. In the analysis of his main works, there are also cases related to national, cultural views and the formation of national literature programs in the years of independence. In the process of research and analysis of Isajon Sultan's works in America, the "Eternal wanderer", "Free" works and several stories are also of great importance.

KEY WORDS: Analysis, methodological requirements, didactic analysis, individual-psychological characteristics, Bloom's taxonomy, cognitive sphere, affective sphere, psychomotor sphere.

INTRODUCTION

Isajon Sultan is one of the great representatives of Uzbek literature. Isajon Sultan was born in 1967 in Rishton district of Fergana region. To this day, he is known as the author of stories and novels for schoolchildren, students of higher education and many readers. The author's first short story "Munojot" helped him gain great fame. After the short story "Munojot" was published in Cholpon publishing house in Tashkent, his creative activity was carried out with some other works. Bloom's taxonomy creates high efficiency in the study and analysis of Isajon Sultan's works. The following are important when applying Bloom's Taxonomy.

1. Knowing;
2. Understanding;
3. Ability to apply;
4. Analysis;
5. Synthesis;
6. Evaluation

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

Pupils test their knowledge by knowing, seeing and checking using modern pedagogical tools. In this process, Isajon Sultan's poems on historical themes such as "Munojot", "The garden of Eram", "Selected Works", "Clear spring", "Eternal Wanderer" play a big role. There are also works created based on literary needs. In this regard, the stories of the creator, such as the story "bowl in water" and "the story of miracles", were published not only in our national newspapers, but also in foreign magazines. The publication of the story of the cup in the water in the literary magazine Russkoya Polin creates a great reality. The story of wonders was published in St. Petersburg literary newspaper in 2013. "Bloom's taxonomy covers different areas of educational activity: cognitive (knowledge), affective (emotional - valuable),

psychomotor (movement). We will dwell on the situation in the process of independent education in each field in improving the competence of students.

1. Cognitive field. As a result of independent repetition of the acquired knowledge in this field, as a result of combining them with the acquired skills and qualifications, new independent activities and exercises are included in the learning objectives related to the need to learn the rules of the law.

2. Affective sphere. In the process of independent work, the formation of interests and inclinations, the formation of the attitude of learning as a result of internal and external psychological influences, and the implementation of it in the practice of activity by understanding it during independent activity are introduced.

3. Psychomotor field. This includes psychological activity in the process of independent work, as a result of physical activity in the processes, goals related to the formation of the skills of centralizing the nerve muscles".[1]

DISCUSSION

To date, in the study and analysis of Isajon Sultan's creative work, familiarization with the details that lead to the analysis of his works, their ideas and various literary tools are of great help. Therefore, Bloom's taxonomy has a great role in teaching Isajon Sultan's creativity to schoolchildren and analyzing his works. Kunduz Husanbayeva's views on creative work with Isajon Sultan were discussed. The main idea and content of the works are enriched with literary details as a result of the lives and relationships of various creators. Comparative analyzes of the works of Abdugafar Rasulov and Isajon Sultan are available. "On the other hand, it is appropriate for the official who is going to observe the lesson to know what to pay attention to, to distinguish between the important and the unimportant in the lesson process, and what are the methodological and pedagogical requirements for the lesson. A teacher who goes to observe a class of a colleague, first of all:

- a) familiarization with the science program, topic, purpose and planning;
- b) organization of textbooks and methodical literature on science;
- d) talk with the teacher about the purpose of the lesson, basic standard requirements (knowledge, knowledge, skills);
- i) knowledge of the composition of the class under analysis; k) It is his responsibility to be aware of the purpose of entering and analyzing the lesson, etc., and to clearly explain this to the teacher.[2]

RESULTS

The artistic analysis of Isajon Sultanov's stories is directly related to folk oral creativity. In this regard, his works can be divided into several groups. For example, in the stories, the events that happen in our daily life and the images in them or the views in the life of a certain society are taken into account. In his novels and short stories, complex topics were touched by their analysis. Examples include my novels with historical themes or themes close to religious themes. We can see that his works have a somewhat serious theme and the pen is shaken. At the same time, you can witness the primary and secondary use of the information that can be given to students in the analysis of stories.

Even a small detail in his works has the ability to form a large generalization. Isajon Sultan is distinguished from other storytellers, short stories and novelists of his time by this very feature. "Today's state of spiritual and educational work in the republic, the participants of the continuous education system: the introduction of teachers into mutual relations, learning

ways to rationally organize pedagogical activities, general secondary schools, lyceums , college students, to determine the ways and means of diagnosing the abilities, talents, knowledge assimilation and education level of students studying in the higher education system; shows the need to create a methodology that ensures its integrity and continuity between educational stages, organize the educational process and enrich its content. The policy of the developing democratic legal state towards young people is to help young men and women to better realize their abilities and talents, to participate more actively in the processes of renewal and development. One of the important factors of improving the quality and efficiency of education is to improve the quality of education and upbringing of students. Pedagogical diagnosis plays an important role in improving the quality and effectiveness of education with students with disabilities".[3] Several of Isajon Sultan's works have been published in Russia and America, and are somewhat different from our country in terms of study in America and Russia. Because of this, there is a need for an individual psychological approach in explaining and organizing the image styles of symbolic stories to foreign readers. Bloom's taxonomy arises in the formation of the ability to know, understand, understand certain forms of information in the world community.

CONCLUSION

Based on Bloom's taxonomy, it is necessary to promote his works, teach them to students, and take into account their figurative and characteristic features. In this regard, the relationship between the affective and cognitive areas, and different approaches in the psychomotor areas, the titles and comments given to them in terms of the works, were given by certain famous people. It can be said that Bloom's taxonomy, which can be taken into account by means of comments, serves as a great tool for analyzing the level of learning of the subject and for the wide implementation of the student's assessment of knowledge levels, as well as for conducting explanatory work. From the point of view of these issues, it is no exaggeration to say that it serves as a great resource for raising the level of consciousness of students and enriching their character traits.

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